

THE MEANING OF THE CONCEPT OF "EDUCATION" AND ITS DIFFERENT INTERPRETATIONS IN

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Abstract: *Education means having the qualities of moral and legal, justice, duty, conscientiousness, responsibility, humanity, good behavior and intelligence. It is necessary from birth to death. This is because of the fact that education is a lifelong process. In this article, we will discuss the original meaning and purpose of education, the correct education of the young generation, educating them to be mature in all aspects of life, as well as the valuable information about education of our famous sages and great thinkers and opinions.*

Key words: *The purpose of education, goodness, justice, loyalty, responsibility, conscience, faith, humanity, good intentions, nobility, the impact of education on society.*

Introduction: Education originated from Arabic word means to take care, to teach, to learn and to protect. Education is a matter of life or death or salvation or

destruction or happiness or disaster for us. In fact, education means having the qualities of moral and legal, justice, duty, consciousness, responsibility, humanity, good behavior and intelligence. It is considered a purposeful activity

directed at achieving certain aims such as transmitting knowledge or fostering skills and character traits. These aims may include the development

of understanding, rationality, kindness, and honesty. Various researchers emphasize the role of critical thinking in order to distinguish education from indoctrination. Some theorists require that education results in an improvement of the student while others prefer a value-neutral definition of the term. In a slightly different sense, education may also refer, not to the process, but to the product of this process: the mental states and dispositions possessed by educated people. Education originated as the transmission of cultural heritage from one generation to the next.

Today, educational goals increasingly encompass new ideas such as the liberation of learners, skills needed for modern society, empathy, and complex vocational skills.

The term Education is a social phenomenon. It has existed since the time of the emergence of individual society. Therefore, in order to be the most perfect breed on the earth, it is necessary to be educated for a person first of all. The education

of young people is considered as an important task in all times, to make them knowledgeable, intelligent and mature in all aspects. Therefore, the main goal of education is to educate the young generation in the spirit of goodness and humanity, as well as patriotism, honesty, and justice. It consists of the process of forming his worldview.

Main body: The development of the young generation into a perfect person and perfect education is considered the greatest wealth not only for a family but also for the whole society in all periods of human life. Because the prosperity of every country on the planet, the happiness of the people living in it, is undoubtedly due to education first, and then teaching. Thus, it is very important to educate young people with moral and legal education, to observe the spirit of patriotism, to arouse emotions such as loyalty, responsibility, conscience, and faith. One of the most famous statements of us¹ Abdurauf Fitrat said: "People act, become statesmen, become happy, gain respect, become brave, become weak, humiliated, put on the cloak of poverty and bear the burden of misfortune, and be ignored, subordinate to others and a slave." children's development

¹H. Omonov, N Khojayev. Pedagogical technologies and

depends on their childhood education, because they receive moral education from the environment and accept the morals of the environment." they get

It is not for nothing that it is said in our nation that the education of a child begins in the mother's womb, the parents should be the first role model for the child, and then the society. It is known that we should treat our children with three things: good upbringing, good education and a good future. The rare works of our thinkers, which have been preserved, encouraged the young generation to grow up to become morally pure and true people. salihin", as well as works, are among these. Among these rare works, first of all, words related to morals and education have a monetary and moral value for commenting on individuals. did not lose. For example:² Muhammad Sadiq Kashgari's work "Odob Salihin" is a source that illuminates high spiritual and moral qualities. Muhammad Sadiq Kashghari's work "Odob salihin" ('Etiquette of good people') is a set of etiquettes that we need to know every minute of our daily life. It is emphasized that if one cannot master the rules of etiquette and is

not polite and clean with good behavior, not only himself, but the whole world will spread evil.

Undoubtedly, there is nothing in the world of life that affects humanity like education. For this reason, famous Western sages have written down valuable information about education since ancient times. The famous Greek philosophers Socrates, Aristotle, Democritus and others They paid serious attention to training, education and training of young people.³Aristotle (384-322 AD) Greece was a highly developed country in the 6th century BC. Aristotle's need for health care: "The state has one production, that is, it is necessary to provide the same education to all individuals." It can be the origin of the neglect of education. Our thinker and great writer ⁴Abdulla Avloni lamented about this and said: "Today, the black face of our society is protected by lowlifes, bad people, orphans, thieves, drug addicts and addicts... children who have not been paid attention to their upbringing." that It follows from this that the young generation of yesterday, whom we did not pay attention to education, will be our weapons tomorrow. Whether our

² Muhammad Sadiq Kashgari "Odob al-salihin"

⁴ Educational and moral views of Abu Nasr Farabi "History of

³ H. Omonov, N Khojayev. Pedagogical technologies and Pedagogogy" 21 pages 60 pages pedagogical skills. Textbook. Tashkent 2009

children are good or bad is the education we gave them yesterday. Therefore, each of us is responsible for the education of the future generation.

According to Farabi, the thinker of the development of the unchanging socio-philosophical thought of the century, education has a great place. After the famous Greek philosopher Aristotle, Farabi, who made a name for himself in the East with his knowledge and the creation of a framework of thought, is considered to be the scientist who first defined education and training. It is possible. Because he can say, he has direct relations with others, follows the rules of society, responds physically to education and serves this society, he considers education to be a human being.

Conclusion: Summarizing the above points, it can be stated that education is a social phenomenon that grows and improves together with humanity from the time of the emergence of individual society until now. The issue of education has been an important and global topic in every era of mankind. As proof of this, we can see the opinions of early scholars such as Aristotle, Aristotle, Farabi, Mahmud Kashgari on the issue of education. Also, it is clear from the above points that the foundation of our future, the future of our people, the spiritual and moral

development directly depends on education. Therefore, a person needs education from the day he is born, his first education is, of course, from his parents, from him. then, every age is directly dependent on the efforts of teachers who have good morals and scientific potential, to set an example for the future young generation. only if he is honest, the whole society will prosper and flourish. According to our ancestors, the eternal treasures of a person in this mortal world are only his good deeds.

REFERENCES:

1. Muhammad Sadiq Kashgari "Odob al-salihin"
2. H. Omonov, N Khojayev. Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills. Textbook. Tashkent 2009
3. Educational and moral views of Abu Nasr Farabi "History of Pedagogy" 21 pages 60 pages
4. library.ziyonet.uz.